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2 **Neighborhood walkability and active ageing: a Difference in differences assessment of**
3 **active transportation over ten years.**

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5
6 **Abstract**

7 The effects of neighborhood morphology and walkability over active travel patterns of ageing
8 older adults are still largely unknown. We used a difference-in-differences design to compare the
9 changes in active transport indicators on older adults ageing for ten years in different areas of the
10 Barcelona Metropolitan Region (Spain). Participants were drawn from two large cross-sectional
11 travel surveys in 2004 and 2014 creating a 10 year span in which they aged from 65-75 y.o. to 75-
12 85y.o. High walkability was associated with more minutes spent walking, and higher odds of
13 meeting Physical Activity (PA) recommendations. Ageing in low walkable areas, in contrast, was
14 associated with lower amounts of PA derived from transportation.

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17 **1. Introduction**

18
19 Europe has one of the most prominent demographic ageing trends worldwide over the next 20
20 years (Walker & Maltby, 2012). With the proportion of people over 65 years old expected to triple
21 in the next half-century (Rechel et al., 2013), ageing has become a significant theme in public
22 policies, from planning to public health (Hooper et al., 2015; Tsai et al., 2015). Both active ageing
23 and ageing in place are important strategies for health promotion among people older than 65 years
24 old. According to the WHO (World Health Organization), 2002 definition, active ageing includes
25 more than just staying mentally and physically active, but also to remain involved and empowered
26 within the community (Rowland, 2013). In the same line, strategies focused on ageing in place
27 aim in part to satisfy the need to avoid unwilling relocation once the ageing process produces a
28 decrease of capabilities, mobility disabilities or loss of independence (Buffel et al., 2012; King et
29 al., 2017).

30 There is now a growing body of research that describes how the built environment can affect
31 multiple outcomes of the ageing process. For environmental gerontologists, how the environment
32 can support physical activity and maintain the independence of older people while they age is of
33 particular interest (Vine et al., 2012). A general consensus exists that walkable environments
34 provide support for higher amounts of physical activity (Ding et al., 2014; Hajna et al., 2015;
35 Hansen, et al., 2013; King et al., 2011) as well as for higher degrees of independence (Clarke &
36 George, 2005; Clarke & Nieuwenhuijsen, 2009) and social engagement (Beard & Petitot, 2011;
37 Hanibuchi et al., 2012; Lager et al., 2015; Leyden, 2003; Zeitler et al., 2012). Overall it is thought
38 that an age-friendly environment can ease the process towards adapting to older adults'
39 diminishing moving capabilities.

40 Many critical aspects of active ageing and ageing in place are encompassed on how the local
41 environment supports the movement and transportation needs of the older population (Winters et
42 al., 2015). Transport is a determinant of health inequalities as it contributes to the existence,
43 persistence, and widening of health disparities inside cities (Giles-Corti et al., 2016). Travel
44 behavior is known to be constructed by a combination of socioeconomic characteristics, built
45 environment possibilities, and the existence of preferences and habits (De Witte et al., 2013), and
46 thus is subjective to change with personal physical changes experienced while ageing. Differences
47 in individual motility –that is, the potential for mobility (Kaufmann & Bergman, 2004)- are
48 determined in part by earlier life decisions, such as that to move outside the city or to reside in an
49 urban, walkable area (Stjernborg et al., 2014). In these cases, ageing in-place forces individuals
50 to adapt to an often unchanged built environment around them (Zeitler et al., 2012). This
51 inadequacy of the built environment to respond to the diminished travel capabilities exacerbates
52 the inability to maintain a normal transportation lifestyle and has been labeled as becoming a
53 prisoner of space (Rowles, 1978); that as one ages in an environment less conducive to comfortable
54 walking they become more and more confined to their home or residential space. This turns to be
55 especially true in Mediterranean societies where residential mobility is low (Angelini & Laferrère,
56 2012) and thus the possibilities of moving to a more favorable built environment are less likely.

57 The decline of physical capabilities usually associated with older adults ageing for 10 years makes
58 the reachable travel area shrink (Weiss, Maantay, & Fahs, 2010) and the availability of desired
59 activity locations near the residence even more important (Marquet & Miralles-Guasch, 2015).
60 Ageing from 65-74 to 75-84 years of age is a crucial stage in life, one that sees a drastic reduction
61 of physical capabilities and puts stress on available possibilities of travel (Yen et al., 2014).
62 Supporting seniors' travel capabilities is important in order to sustain their quality of life, including
63 not only their most basic sustenance needs, but also secondary needs like social interaction or
64 leisure, that are also crucial for their well-being (Sikder & Pinjari, 2012). The failure to support
65 travel needs by the local environment can lead to individuals becoming not only more sedentary
66 but also less social (Richard et al., 2009) and can lead eventually to isolation (Stjernborg et al.,
67 2014). In particular, low walkable environments have been found correlated with lower Physical
68 Activity (PA) levels (Michael et al., 2006) and lower frequency of walking (Zeitler et al., 2012).
69 On the other hand a number of studies have found some built environment characteristics, such as,
70 density, land use mix and connectivity, to foster walking for transport in older adults (Frank et al.,
71 2010; Li et al., 2005). Studies have also found how vital environments are to encourage older
72 adults to walk (Marquet & Miralles-Guasch, 2015). Walking for transport is an important source
73 of PA for older adults, who particularly need to remain active in order to prevent chronic disease
74 and maintain everyday basic physical functions (Pahor et al., 2014). The built environment thus
75 has a central role in enabling ageing in place and in facilitating opportunities for the development
76 of healthy behaviors in later life.

77 A lack of evidence exists however, when it comes to actually understanding how the walkability
78 of the environment can affect healthy travel behaviors after ageing in specific environments for
79 long periods of time. In other words, while the impacts of *living* in a low/high walkable

80 environment have been properly studied, there is no such research on the effects of *ageing* for 5 or
81 10 years in high/low environments. The focus has thus to change from a static view of the effects
82 of walkability to a dynamic and accumulative view of how spending the ageing life stage in a
83 particular environment can affect healthy behaviors.

84 The term walkability is often used in the literature to define an environment that meets the
85 necessary morphological and functional features to not only enable walking as an everyday mode
86 of transport, but also to promote it (Leslie et al., 2007). It is usually associated with high levels of
87 population density, land use mix, and measures of connectivity and design (Ewing & Handy,
88 2009). In particular, there is a need to understand the effects of the environment not in older adults
89 who reside in an environment in a moment of time but in older adults that age through the years in
90 a particular urban environment. The accumulated effects of living in a place with particular
91 conditions can be additive, especially in sensitive life-stages. To better understand these effects,
92 more longitudinal and experimental research is needed to give additional weight to the findings
93 achieved using cross-sectional methods (Beard & Petitot, 2011). Unfortunately, longitudinal
94 studies are scarce and almost all of them include a short follow-up period. A recent review found
95 only two longitudinal studies involving ageing that included ten or more years of follow-up (Beard
96 & Petitot, 2011) Others have found an overall prevalence of cross-sectional studies (Haselwandter
97 et al., 2015). Only Hirsch et al., (2014) provide a notable exception with a longitudinal study that
98 has no parallel on the European context and that does not focus exclusively on seniors. In that
99 situation, the use of alternative methodologies like difference in differences can provide additional
100 findings by mimicking the functioning of longitudinal studies. Difference in Differences (DiD)
101 methods allow us to compare the paralel evolution of trends in two different areas or groups of
102 population. Here we use DiD to address the gap in the literature and to investigate how much of
103 the age-related change in travel behavior is attributable to walkability. By investigating how older
104 adults' travel behavior change as they age across two time points and in two neighborhood
105 designations, we are able to understand the role of low and high walkable environment in the
106 promotion and maintenance of healthy travel habits as we age.

107 2. **Methods:**

108 The present study was based on two cross-sectional surveys taken in 2004 and 2014 and covering
109 the Barcelona Metropolitan Region in Spain. The main data source of the study is the EMEF
110 (Enquesta de Mobilitat en dia Feiner) travel survey, an official wide-ranging travel survey taken
111 periodically by the Catalonia (Spain) government as a joint initiative of the Department of
112 Territorial Policy and Public Works and the Metropolitan Transport Authority of Barcelona, Spain.
113 The aim of the survey is to describe the transportation habits of the resident population in the
114 Metropolitan Region of Barcelona. The survey is taken every year, employing a computer-assisted
115 telephone interviewing (CATI) technique to interview a representative sample of the population
116 using simple random sampling. The 2004 edition of the survey had a total sample of 4642 people,
117 while the 2014 edition had a total sample of 8851 (IERMB, 2014). The Barcelona Metropolitan
118 Region offers an appropriate context to study contrasts on walkability effects, given the high

119 disparity of its urban morphology, with highly dense and urbanized walkable areas lying in close
120 proximity to areas developed around sprawled and car oriented environments (Marquet &
121 Miralles-Guasch, 2017).

122 Using data from the 2004 (T₁) and 2014 (T₂) editions of the EMEF, the present study selects the
123 participants that were between 65 and 74 years of age in the 2004 edition (n=552; mean age=69.5;
124 SD=2.84), and the participants that were between 75 and 84 years of age in the 2014 edition
125 (n=748; mean age=79.1; SD=2.67). By doing so, we tried to mimic the ageing process of a single
126 cohort for ten years from 2004 (T₁) and 2014 (T₂), despite our data not being longitudinal in nature.
127 At the same time, by using 65-74 and 75-84 we are focusing on a crucial stage of the ageing process
128 marked by the appearance of some frailty symptoms such as weight loss and physical capability
129 decline (Harrison & Ragland, 2003; Michael, et al., 2014). Table 1 displays the variables extracted
130 from the EMEF surveys along with the sample sizes for (T₁) and (T₂). Chi-square values indicate
131 whether there has been a significant change in each category across the two time points.

132

133

134 Table 1: Sample size and change between time points

Table 1:
Sample size and change between time points

Variables	T ₁ (n=552)		T ₂ (n=748)		X ² (<i>p</i> value)
	n	(%)	n	(%)	
Gender					1.03 (0.170)
Male	239	43.3	321	40.5	-
Female	313	56.7	471	59.5	-
Education					
None	146	26.5	189	24.5	1.16 (0.155)
Primary	300	54.5	383	49.7	4.67 (0.018)
Secondary/college	104	18.9	199	25.8	7.36 (0.004)
Walkability					
Low	189	34.2	360	45.5	16.93 (<0.001)
High	267	48.4	300	37.9	14.69 (<0.001)
Household size					
<= 1	154	27.9	327	41.3	25.38 (<0.001)
2	300	54.3	416	52.5	0.43 (0.273)
3+	98	17.8	49	6.2	44.68 (<0.001)

All variables except gender are treated as dummy variables.

135

136 **Walkability index:**

137 The walkability of the built environment was computed at the smallest administrative unit
 138 available –municipal level-, following Frank et al., (2005) method. The median size of the
 139 municipalities was of 7787 inhabitants (IQR 15451). The method was adapted to substitute the
 140 connectivity measures (which were not available) for an additional land-use measure that
 141 calculated the share of walkable land-uses versus non-walkable uses in a method similar to that
 142 used by Forsyth et al., (2008). This extra land-use measure, extracted from cadastral reference,
 143 also helps overcome some of the deficits associated with the use of entropy scores as the core of
 144 walkability indexes (Brown et al., 2009). All variables were computed using 2010 data, setting a
 145 convenient middle point in our timeline. Our walkability index was thus defined by:

146
$$\text{Walkability index} = (\text{Zlanduse_mix} + \text{Znet_density} + \text{Zlanduse_walk}) / 3$$

147 Where Zlanduse_mix is an entropy land-use score extracted directly from Frank et al., (2005),
 148 Znet_density is the standardized result of dividing the total population by the residential area, and
 149 Zlanduse_walk is a sum of weighted z-scores of walkable land-uses (compact residential areas;
 150 historic buildings; pre-1950 buildings; facilities; mixed developments; retail areas) after
 151 subtracting the weighted z-scores of un-walkable land-uses such as residential areas consisting of
 152 row houses or detached housing. A high score in our walkability index represents an area with a

153 high presence of walkable land-uses, a high net population density, and a high land-use mixture.
154 Walkability of the administrative units was ordered and cut points for low and high walkability
155 were set at the lower and higher tertiles respectively.

156

157 **Difference in Differences (DiD)**

158

159 We use DiD to compare trends in healthy travel patterns between low walkable areas and a pre-
160 determined control population that is not exposed to living in low walkable urban environments.
161 The DiD methodology has been used extensively in both public health and transportation studies
162 to estimate differences in the mean value of an outcome for two or more populations over a specific
163 time period (Alam et al., 2015; Belanger-Gravel et al., 2015, 2016; Benmarhania et al., 2013;
164 Reeves & de Vries, 2016). This approach is based on a comparison of differences over time
165 between two comparable groups and two points in time. In the specific case of this study, we
166 compare the change of a travel indicator (i.e. trips per day) between 2004 and 2014 among seniors
167 living in low walkable areas, with the change of that same indicator and period of time registered
168 among people living in high walkable areas. The two compared groups need not to be identical,
169 however, using the DiD approach implies a common trend assumption (Vandoros et al., 2013).
170 That is, to assume that the change in the selected indicator would have been equal in both study
171 areas if there was no difference in the walkability of the built environment. Our assumption is that
172 no differences in the change of active travel indicators should be found when comparing the two
173 populations ageing in different areas (Dimick & Ryan, 2014), and thus, whatever differences
174 between low and high walkable areas are found, are attributable to the effect of walkability. In
175 other words, if walkability played no effect, no significant differences would be found in the
176 changes of travel indicators between two groups of older adults ageing for ten years.

177 We first use older adults living in low walkable areas of the Metropolitan Region of Barcelona as
178 the study group and older adults living in every other area as control group. In a second analysis,
179 we use older adults living in high walkable areas as study group and older adults living in every
180 other area as control group. In both cases respondents from the 2004 survey constituted the sample
181 at T_1 and those coming from the 2014 survey constituted the sample at T_2 . We assumed that if the
182 walkability of the neighborhood had no effect on senior's travel behaviors, the differences in
183 everyday travel indicators between the group living in low walkability and the group living in high
184 walkability should be the same when ageing from T_1 to T_2 .

185 To test the differences in active travel that are attributable to walkability, we used six indicators
186 that are commonly used in active ageing and gerontology literature. Those selected indicators were
187 (1) immobility, expressed as whether the interviewed person left their home on the day of the
188 interview or not (Sikder & Pinjari, 2012) (2) time invested in active modes of transport, computed
189 as the average number of minutes spent walking/cycling per day and per person (Aird & Buys,
190 2015; Rojas-Rueda et al., 2016), (3) activity engagement, computed as the average number of trips
191 taken per person per day regardless of the mode of transport used (Prins et al., 2014; Scheiner,

192 2014) (4) time spent driving, computed as the average number of minutes spent driving per day
193 and per person, (Rosenbloom, 2004) (5) time spent in transportation,-computed as the average
194 number of minutes spent in any mode of transport per day and per person, (Giuliano, 1999) and
195 (6) share of people who solely through transportation achieved the World Health Organization
196 (WHO, 2010) and the Center for Disease Control (CDC) PA recommendations, which was
197 calculated as percentage of overall population achieving more than 30min of PA derived from
198 transport, per day.

199 Data on gender, education level and household size were used as covariates for all the models.
200 Gender has been repeatedly found to significantly affect transport behavior changes related to
201 ageing (Scheiner, 2014; Stjernborg et al., 2014). Education is used here as a proxy for income
202 level. Finally, household size is a key determinant of older adult's mobility (Haustein & Siren,
203 2015) as it defines if the older adult is living alone or with other potentially supporting individuals.
204 Living with others can provide social support and help for traveling out of the home, reducing
205 immobility rates (Sikder & Pinjari, 2012). At the same time, living with others can generate less
206 need to travel for maintenance purposes, reducing the number of daily trips (Evans, 2001).

207 In addition to descriptive statistics, we used difference-in-difference models to estimate the effect
208 of walkability on active travel patterns of the ageing population. Due to sample size, immobility
209 could not be included in the final models. DiD models mimic experimental research using
210 observational data by comparing the change in the intervention group (in our case those living in
211 low walkable areas) with the average change in the non-intervention group (in our case all the
212 population not living in low walkable areas) (Reeves & de Vries, 2016). This modeling estimates
213 differences in active travel behavior at T₁ and ten years later at T₂ for people living in low walkable
214 environments versus people not living in low walkable environments:

$$215 \text{ Effect of Walkability} = (I_{T2 \cdot \text{low_walkability}} - I_{T1 \cdot \text{low_walkability}}) - (I_{T2 \cdot \text{all_other_walkabilities}} - I_{T1 \cdot \text{all_other_walkabilities}})$$

216 Where "I" is a measure of active traveling among a particular group of people (those living in low
217 walkable areas, vs all others) at a particular time (pre - and post-ageing). "I" is a vector of six
218 different active travel measures as described above.

219 Using the above equation in a regression model we write the DiD estimator as:

$$220 Y = \beta_1 \text{Walkability} + \beta_2 \text{Time} + \beta_3 \text{Walkability} * \text{Time}$$

221 Where β_1 is the estimated mean difference in Y (active travel indicator) between the treatment
222 (low walkability) and control groups (others) before the ten years have passed (T₁). β_2 is the
223 expected mean change in the active travel indicator from before to after the ten-year span among
224 the control group (those not living in low walkable areas). Finally, β_3 is the DiD estimator. In
225 addition, we also compute the sum of $\beta_1 + \beta_3$ to obtain the estimated mean difference in the active
226 travel indicator between the low walkable areas and the control group after the ten years.

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228

229 3. Results:

230 3.1 Low walkable areas:

231 The first analysis focused on estimating how living in a low walkable area could be affecting the
232 active travel indicators. Descriptive statistics can be found in Table 2 and Figure 1. People ageing
233 in low walkable areas for instance, registered in T₁ a lower immobility rate (16.9%) than those
234 living in control areas (17.4%). With the ageing process (changing from T₁ to T₂) however, this
235 relationship seems to invert, producing a higher increase in immobility in low walkable areas
236 (2.7% vs 2.1%) by making the immobility rate in low walkable areas (19.6%) surpass that of the
237 control areas (19.5%). The difference in differences between years was thus reduced (-0.6) by the
238 means of immobility rates in low walkable areas increasing more than that of the other areas.

239 **Insert Figure 1** Effects of low walkability on healthy active travel indicators.

240 While walkability seemed to have no effect on the average number of trips taken daily (DiD=0.01)
241 it did generate important variances in terms of time invested in the different modes of transport.
242 The most important differences can be found on the average time invested in walking (DiD=9.56).
243 Walked time was almost equal to T₁ (43.8m vs 44.0m) but in T₂ it dropped by almost ten minutes
244 (-9.3) in low walkable areas while remaining stable in the control areas (+0.3m). Time invested in
245 driving, in contrast, seems to have dropped equally by 2-3 minutes (-2.8m vs -2.3m). The drop in
246 walking time generated an 8.8% DiD in the overall number of people achieving PA
247 recommendations. The ageing process reduced the number of people above the PA
248 recommendations by 7.1% in low walkable areas, while in other areas this proportion was slightly
249 increased (1.7%).

250

Table 2

Effects of low walkability on healthy active travel indicators.

	T₁	T₂	Change T₂ - T₁	DiD
Immobility				
Low Walkability	16.9%	19.6%	2.7%	
Others	17.5%	19.5%	2.1%	
Difference	-0.6%*	0.1%		-0.50
No. of Trips				
Low Walkability	2.59	2.59	0.00	
Others	2.94	2.95	0.01	
Difference	-0.35**	-0.36*		0.01
Total Minutes Walked				
Low Walkability	43.8	34.5	-9.3	
Others	44.0	44.3	0.3	
Difference	-0.2*	-9.8*		9.6
Total Minutes Driving				
Low Walkability	13.8	11.0	-2.77	
Others	6.4	4.0	-2.34	
Difference	-7.4*	-7.0**		-0.4
Total Minutes Travelling				
Low Walkability	66.0	54.8	-11.5	
Others	70.7	68.7	-2.04	
Difference	-4.7*	-13.8*		9.1
Meeting PA guidelines				
Low Walkability	47.1%	40.0%	-7.1%	
Others	46.3%	48.0%	1.7%	
Difference	0.8	-8**		8.8

*Significant difference at <0.01 level (Levene's test)

** Significant difference at <0.001 level (Levene's test)

252

253 The DiD model, adjusted by gender, education, and household size (Table 3), reveals low
 254 walkability at T₁ to be associated with shorter total times invested in transport, longer times
 255 invested in driving, and overall fewer number of trips made per day than those living in the control
 256 areas. In terms of the ageing effects, the model found a significant drop in both the total minutes
 257 spent walking and the total minutes spent driving. Finally, when assessing the effect of low
 258 walkability on ageing, the adjusted model only found a negative association regarding participants
 259 achieving the PA recommendations.

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261
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Table 3

Adjusted difference-in-differences estimates of the impact of low walkability on healthy active travel indicators

	Total Time Walking		Total Time Travelling		Total Time Driving		No. of Trips		Meets PA	
	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI
Low Walkable (β_1)	-1.67	-18.7;1.52	-1.94*	-23.4;0.1	2.37*	1.10; 11.4	-2.07*	-0.8;-0.0	-0.07	-0.1;0.1
Post ageing (2014) (β_2)	-2.17*	-17.2;-0.8	-2.35*	-20.6;-1.8	-1.63	-7.6; 0.7	-2.81*	-0.7;-0.1	0.15	-0.1;0.1
Low Walkable * Post ageing (β_3)	-0.36	-15.3;10.5	-0.32	-17.3;12.5	0.28	-5.6; 7.5	0.25	-0.4;0.5	-1.77**	-0.2;0.0
$\beta_1 + \beta_3$	-2.03		-2.26		2.65		-1.82		-1.84	

***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

^a All adjusted models control for Gender (male/female), education level (none/primary/secondary or college), and household size (one person/two persons/three or more)

263

264 3.2 High walkable areas:

265 The second part of the analysis was focused on analyzing the effect of high walkable environments
266 on active ageing. Table 4 and Figure 2 present the descriptive statistics depicting travel habits of
267 older adults living in high walkable environments compared with every other senior living in the
268 Metropolitan region.

269 **Insert Figure 2** Effects of high walkability on healthy active travel indicators.

270 High walkability had a positive effect on immobility. The general trend in the Metropolitan Region
271 was that immobility increased from T₁ to T₂ (+4.5%). Those people living in high walkable areas
272 however remained active for a longer period of time (0.2%). In terms of activity engagement,
273 measured by the number of trips taken on an average day, older adults in high walkable areas were
274 reducing their average number of trips by 6%, while the rest of the Metropolitan Region was doing
275 so by 13%. High walkability also affected the amount of time spent in modes of transport. The
276 total amount of minutes walked was reduced by 1.9 minutes in high walkability areas between T1
277 and T2, while this time was reduced by almost eight minutes (7.9m) in the rest of the region. This
278 generated a DiD of 9.7 minutes. These opposite trends were not found in the total amount of time
279 spent driving, where we both low walkable areas and the overall region decreased their driving
280 minutes. It is noteworthy that high walkable areas decreased their driving time by 29% and the rest
281 of the areas did so only by 25%. Finally, the total amount of time invested in transportation dropped
282 across the Metropolitan Region with a 14.9% reduction (from 65.9 minutes to 56.1), but only by
283 1.3% in the high walkable areas (from 72.5 minutes to 71.6).

284 Each of the above findings impacts older adults achieving PA recommendations. In T1, older
285 adults living in high walkable areas were less likely to achieve this recommendation, but this trend
286 changed in T₂ as the number of people above the 30m of PA dropped by 7.1% in the whole

287 Metropolitan Region. In high walkable areas, in contrast, T₂ registered a higher share of older
 288 adults achieving the PA recommendations than before, with a 4.4% increase.

289

Table 4
 Effects of high walkability on healthy active travel indicators.

		T ₁	T ₂	Change T ₂ - T ₁	DiD
Immobility					
	High Walkability	16.9%	17.1%	0.2%	
	Others	17.5%	22.0%	4.5%	
	Difference	-0.6	-4.9		4.3
No. of Trips					
	High Walkability	3.25	3.05	-0.20	
	Others	2.99	2.60	-0.39	
	Difference	0.26*	0.45		0.19
Total Minutes Walked					
	High Walkability	42.0	43.9	1.9	
	Others	45.6	37.7	-7.9	
	Difference	-3.6	6.2		9.7
Total Minutes Driving					
	High Walkability	5.8	4.1	-1.7	
	Others	11.9	8.9	-3.0	
	Difference	-6.1**	-4.8**		1.3
Total Minutes Travelling					
	High Walkability	72.5	71.6	-0.9	
	Others	65.9	56.1	-9.8	
	Difference	6.6	15.5		8.9
Meeting PA guidelines					
	High Walkability	45.6%	50.0%	4.4%	
	Others	47.5%	40.4%	-7.1%	
	Difference	-1.9	9.6*		11.5

*Significant difference at <0.01 level (Levene's test)

** Significant difference at <0.001 level (Levene's test)

290

291 In the DiD model (Table 5), adjusted by gender, education level, and household size, living in high
 292 walkable environments was positively associated with almost every indicator of active ageing.
 293 DiD increased for walking minutes (1.83), total time invested in transport (1.05) and achieving the
 294 PA recommendations (1.82).

295

Table 5

Adjusted difference-in-differences estimates of the impact of high walkability on healthy active travel indicators

	Total Time Walking		Total Time Travelling		Total Time Driving		No. of Trips		Meets PA	
	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI
High Walkable (β_1)	-0.70*	-12.2;5.8	0.99*	-5.5;16.7	-3.63***	-13.9;-4.2	1.98**	0.0;0.7	-0.28	-0.1;0.1
Post ageing (2014) (β_2)	-2.17**	-16.7;-0.8	-3.20***	-25.9;-6.2	-2.14**	-9.1;-0.4	-2.41**	-0.7;-0.1	-2.15**	-0.2;-0.0
High Walkable * Post ageing (β_3)	1.83**	-0.8;22.8	1.05*	-6.8;22.5	1.17*	-2.6;10.3	-0.23	-0.5;0.4	1.82**	-0.0;0.2
$\beta_1 + \beta_3$	1.13		2.04		-2.46		1.76		1.54	

***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

^a All adjusted models control for gender (male/female), education level (none/primary/secondary or college), and household size (one person/two persons/three or more)

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4. Discussion:

302 Our analysis tries to quantify the effects of walkability on the reduction of mobility and active
 303 travel associated with the ageing process (Evans, 2001). Despite numerous recent efforts to
 304 understand the association between built environment and physical activity in older adults, a lack
 305 of consensus still exists due to differences in methods and the abundance of confounding factors
 306 (Weiss et al., 2010).

307 Our results seem to confirm the link between walkability and immobility among older people.
 308 Despite the DiD method prevents us from establishing causality, these results seem to validate the
 309 general narrative that links mobility with the potential to reach activity locations within each
 310 person's potential travel area (Patterson & Farber, 2015). As ageing limits travel capabilities,
 311 having destinations closer to home and walkable environments becomes increasingly important at
 312 defining mobility/immobility. Maintaining mobility rates and decreasing immobility however, is
 313 not the same. Immobile older adults, defined as those that did not leave their home on the day prior
 314 to the interview, are the ones most at risk of social exclusion and thus deserve special treatment
 315 and attention. Some authors have noted however that immobility rates have to be treated carefully,
 316 as they can often be biased as a form of soft refusal to participate in travel surveys travel surveys
 317 typically ask for data on only one date, and some activities tend to go under-reported (Hubert &
 318 Armoogum, 2008). Even with acknowledging this, our results appear to support with data the
 319 assumption already made by Sikder & Pinjari (2012) that walkability can reduce the number of
 320 older adults secluded in their homes.

321 Even if the older adult does not qualify as immobile, their travel capabilities may very well be
322 constrained and affected by the environment. Ageing in the suburbs has been seen by some as a
323 process of increasing constraints, caused both by personal physical capacity and the increasing
324 inadequacy of the lived environment (Stjernborg et al., 2014). Ageing in place requires an
325 adaptation that can be either eased or hindered by the conditions of the environment. When the
326 environment is characterized by its low walkability, our analysis finds a decrease in most
327 significant travel indicators, from total walked minutes, to the overall number of trips. In contrast,
328 older adults living in high walkable areas maintained high activity engagement rates, with more
329 than three trips per day, on average. These indicators of frequent travel, even at later life-stage, are
330 consistent with the findings by Winters et al., (2015) in high walkable areas in Canada. Our study
331 however differs from that of Winters et al., in that our definition of walkability stemmed from land
332 use, and density indicators, whereas their study used *Walk Score* data. The use of different
333 walkability measures prevents direct comparison between studies, as the *Walk Score* index is
334 computed based on the number of key locations (i.e. stores, retail, services) in a one mile radius
335 around an address (Duncan et al., 2016), and GIS based walkability indexes are created based on
336 land use mixtures, density, connectivity and other urban attributes. It is relevant thus to confirm
337 the apparent link between walkability and higher activity engagement –expressed by a higher trip
338 frequency- is sustained not only through different geographical contexts but also different
339 methodologies. Additionally, results suggest that the difference in the number of daily trips is
340 associated with high walkability, and not lower walkability. From a policy perspective, it is not
341 enough to focus on the absence of low walkable areas, but instead there is value in terms of health
342 prevention and senior’s well-being in investing specifically in high walkability areas.

343 Older adults living in high walkable areas clearly demonstrate healthier travel behaviors in both
344 T₁ and T₂ compared with their counterparts living elsewhere. Inversely, older adults living in low
345 walkable areas proved to have travel behaviors less healthy than their counterparts living
346 elsewhere. Regarding the particular use of walking, results extend the findings of Frank et al.,
347 (2010) showing that walkability is not only positively associated with walking more often, but also
348 with walking for longer periods of time. They also concur with results from Hirsch et al., (2014)
349 associating particular urban characteristics linked with walkability –such as density, land use mix
350 and connectivity- with more minutes invested in walking for transport. In our case, only high
351 walkability levels seem to be significantly associated with the retention of extended walking times
352 as people age, as no significant differences in walking times are found in those who age in low
353 walkable areas. However this is a point that could be affected by the particular differences between
354 European and US urban areas. Our mean population density was 44% higher than that of Hirsch
355 et al., and with higher levels of density and land use mix, it is to be expected that our low-walkable
356 high-walkable designations are also different of those by Frank et al., (2010). Overall, ten years
357 later those living in highly walkable areas were walking for 10 more minutes a day than their
358 counterparts living in low walkable areas. This represented a 27.4% difference in the daily walked
359 minutes associated with walkability. In weekly terms, these observed differences are even larger
360 than the 30 min/week reported by King et al., (2011) for the US context. Most importantly, these
361 differences are generated almost entirely in the 10-year ageing span that goes from T¹ to T², which
362 further increases planners’ incentive to provide walkable environments.

363 Time invested in driving, in contrast, seems to have dropped equally by 2-3 minutes (-2.77m vs -
364 2.33m), in both walkable and non-walkable areas. This perpetuates the already existent differences
365 with those living in low walkable areas driving 2.75 times more than those living in the control
366 areas (11m vs 4m). Being able to continue a functional life after cessation of driving has been
367 reported as a major concern for older adults wanting to age in place (Kerr et al., 2012). The fact
368 that people living in high walkable areas can sustain an ageing process with higher travel rates and
369 lower driving times is thus a healthy indicator.

370 Finally, a relevant indicator regarding active ageing is whether walkability helps or hinders the
371 capacity of older adults to reach physical activity recommendations as they age. Given the
372 particular need for older adults to increase the amount of PA that they obtain from unstructured
373 and non-recreational activities (Hekler et al., 2012), the potential of encouraging walking for
374 transport through the design of the built environment is especially appealing (King et al., 2011).
375 The positive association between walkability and reaching the recommended amount of physical
376 activity is sustained through the adjusted and unadjusted results. Those living and ageing in highly
377 walkable areas are more likely to get more than 30 minutes of PA from their travelling than those
378 both in the control and the low walkable areas. These results partially contradict other studies that
379 have found no correlation between walkability and chances of getting close to the PA
380 recommendations (Frank et al., 2010; King et al., 2011; Owen et al., 2007) and aligns with the
381 group of studies that have found some of these associations (Hajna et al., 2015). In our case, it is
382 important to clarify that our adjusted model does not find a significant difference at T^1 between
383 those older adults living in high and low walkability areas. The DiD model finds significance in
384 the change between T^1 and T^2 , or as the ageing process occurs in a high or low walkable area. This
385 seems to imply walkability does not significantly affect the chances of getting 30 min of daily PA
386 in older adults between 65-74 years of age, instead walkability does play an important role in
387 defining the chances of older adults between 75-84 years of age. This is consistent with the built
388 environment gaining relevance as the age advances and mobility capabilities decay (Rechel et al.,
389 2013).

390 This study has some limitations. First and foremost, DiD studies come with some important
391 limitations when compared with full longitudinal randomized studies, and thus, results have to be
392 interpreted with caution. On the other hand, they also provide advantages like the larger 10-year'
393 time span and the inclusion of larger population samples. Similarly, we had data on older adults'
394 PA derived only from transport. It is possible that older adults in low walkable areas may be
395 compensating for their lack of transport-derived PA by engaging in voluntary and scheduled
396 physical activities, although recent research indicates that this is actually not happening (King et
397 al., 2017). Similarly, getting 30min of PA from transport does not automatically entail reaching
398 PA recommendations. Most analysis of senior travel behavior highlight the importance of car
399 ownership and driving cessation. However, we could not account for that due to the fact that the
400 2014 edition of the survey did not have any question regarding car ownership.

401 Furthermore, our results potentially suffer from some form of selection bias, as we cannot be sure
402 that the population sampled at T^1 is still in the sample at T^2 . At T^2 for instance, there is a major
403 prevalence of people with a college degree than at T^1 . In order to account for this and other

404 differences of the sample one should interpret the unadjusted results with caution. Similarly,
405 although the DiD method mimics an experimental design, not being a longitudinal study prevents
406 us from establishing causation. Having said that, our samples reached a similar distribution across
407 the different types of built environments, and while there were differences in the distribution of
408 population between low and high walkability from T1 to T2, these were due to the sample size in
409 T2 being larger than in T1, as neither the low walkability nor the high walkability areas lost
410 population. Also, the fact that residential mobility is highly infrequent at advanced ages, especially
411 in Spain makes us confident that both surveys at T¹ and T² were sampled from the same population.
412 In the same way, the 10-year span between T¹ (2004) and T² (2014) introduces important elements
413 of variability, the most evident one being the economic crisis, that may have altered the conditions
414 in which older adults are living and created unexpected outcomes. The advent of the crisis however
415 provides us also with a positive element for our study. The lack of resources has almost paralyzed
416 infrastructure investments and real estate developments between 2007 and 2014 freezing the urban
417 environments and making the comparison between areas from T¹ to T² more feasible. All studies
418 using difference in differences methodology are subject to be affected by unobservable differential
419 changes between the two study groups. However, in our opinion our sample meets the two main
420 assumptions of difference in differences analysis: parallel trends and common shocks (Dimick &
421 Ryan, 2014). Using a travel survey as a primary data source also entails a limitation on the amount
422 of information available regarding the personal characteristics. A health survey with detailed travel
423 data would have provided valuable information regarding perceived health status and
424 walking/mobility difficulties (Cavoli et al., 2015). Finally, using only home walkability as a
425 reference may result in some erroneous findings, as older people can travel to more walkable areas
426 during the day. However, this is a common error in most studies in the field and its effects are
427 attenuated as the population involved -older adults- is characterized by a lack of work-related travel
428 and a preference for proximity traveling around home (Marquet & Miralles-Guasch, 2015).

429 Overall, the present study has used differences in differences approach to mimic the functioning
430 of a longitudinal study and to analyze not only the travel behavior of older adults living in each
431 environment, but also travel behavior change as older adults age. Identifying these trends is a
432 crucial part of understanding the potential and limitations of ageing in place, as it eliminates
433 potential self-selection bias that arises from most cross-sectional studies linking walkability with
434 higher physical activity in later ages of life (Beard & Petitot, 2011; Lee et al., 2009). Here the use
435 of DiD methods provides evidence to claim not only that older adults living in high walkable areas
436 have healthier transportation habits, but also that they develop healthier trends as they age. At the
437 same time, living in low walkable areas places older adults in a difficult situation that often leads
438 to less healthy travel patterns. As other studies have found, living in non-walkable environments
439 may hurt PA even if the older adults involved are willingly attempting to increase their regular
440 physical activity levels, as they often occur with compensatory reduction of other active behaviors
441 such as active transport (King et al., 2017).

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443 **5. References:**

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680 **Figure 1:** Effects of low walkability on healthy mobility indicators.

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683 **Figure 2:** Effects of high walkability on healthy mobility indicators.

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